

EXPLORING THE INKED FUTURE: A STUDY ON THE TATTOO INTENTIONS OF GEN Z

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates tattoo intentions among Gen Z individuals aged 18 to 27 in Valenzuela City. The study engaged selected participants (n=100), all lacking tattoos, who shared their perspectives on potential future ink through Likert-scale responses. Utilizing a survey instrument covering critical factors such as [1] Subjective Norms, [2] Perceived Behavioral Control, and [3] Attitude, the research aimed to uncover unique insights. The findings indicate a strong correlation between tattoo intention and Subjective Norms ($\alpha=3.30$; $SD=.74$) and Perceived Behavioral Control ($\alpha=2.71$; $SD=.70$), while Attitude ($\alpha=2.87$; $SD=.76$) was not found to have a significant impact. Additionally, the correlation analysis revealed strong links between Perceived Behavioral Control ($r=.692$; $p=.003$), Subjective Norms ($r=.714$; $p=.001$), and Attitude ($r=.611$; $p=.239$). Crucially, the study offers complex explanations for Gen Z's tattoo aspirations in Valenzuela City, emphasizing the impact of perceived behavioral control and subjective norms. The p-value of Subjective Norms was less than 0.05 (0.001), as a result, Subjective Norm is a significant predictor of tattoo intention. The p-value of Perceived Behavioral Control was less than 0.05 (0.001), as a result, Perceived Behavioral Control is also a significant predictor of tattoo intention. Ultimately, this study highlights the significant impact of subjective norms and perceived behavioral control on the tattoo intentions of Generation Z individuals in Valenzuela City. On the other hand, there are strong connections between

attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, but attitude is not a significant predictor.

Keywords: *Attitude, Correlation, Gen Z, Influence, Intention, Marketing Students, Perceived Behavioral Control, Predictor, Subjective Norm*

INTRODUCTION

Tattoos have experienced a rise in demand and popularity since the 1970s but more suddenly in the last 15 to 20 years. Over the past 20 years, there has been a noticeable increase in the level of tolerance and acknowledgement of tattoos within churches, educational institutions and professional workplaces (Roeloff, 2023). In recent years, tattoos have depicted historical boundaries to become a profound form of self-expressions, embodying individual narratives, cultural significance, personal aesthetics and body art enthusiasts.

Due to the diverse range of perceptions and influences surrounding tattoos, it presents a complex challenge for Gen Z individuals contemplating tattoo intentions. The influence of familial, peer, cultural and media influences creates numerous conflicting messages and ideals about body art. However, despite the increased acceptance of tattoos, professional and social stigma are still on the rise in certain professional settings, potentially impacting job prospects or social perceptions. Amidst the constantly evolving perceptions of society towards tattoos, tattoo artists encounter considerable challenges in effectively marketing their services and adapting to the shifting preferences in body art. This dynamic environment poses difficulties in planning marketing strategies that resonate with the diverse expectations of Gen Z.

This study hints at a connection between permanent body art and personal perception, suggesting it might influence how we see ourselves in terms of personality and willingness to push boundaries. (Drews et al., 2000) this study uncovered a connection between having a tattoo and risk taking behaviors like substance use and risky sex, though it found no link to suicidal thoughts or actions. (King et al., 2013). Forget just about cool aesthetics for Gen Z, tattoos are ink-woven storytellers. (Morton, R. (2006), According to study tattoos are no longer a fringe trend relegated to rebellious youth. We witness the tap of the tattoo needle echoing generations of wisdom, each mark a testament to tradition. In the review of related literature for the thesis on tattoo intentions among Gen Z, existing studies were examined to understand the motivations and societal factors influencing this generation's decision to get tattoos. (Abellan et al., 2022). The literature highlighted themes such as self-expression, identity formation, and cultural influences as significant drivers for tattoo adoption. Additionally, societal perceptions and evolving norms regarding tattoos were explored to contextualize Gen Z's attitudes toward body art. (Colonno, 2023). The synthesis of these findings contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the motivations behind tattoo choices among the Gen Z demographic. (Forbes, 2001).

The researchers aimed to explore the major factor that shaped the tattoo intentions among Gen Z individuals. Researchers used a theory known as the Theory of Reasoned Action and was given a new name: the Theory of Planned Behavior (Brookes, 2023). It attempted to investigate and comprehend the ways in which respondents' decisions to get tattoos were influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

The study depicts valuable insights into the intricate dynamics influencing Gen Z' tattoo intentions within the context of understanding how the multifaceted factors contribute to their decision-making process. This comprehensive study derived an understanding of how tattoo artists can be empowered and how they could offer actionable strategies to tailor their marketing approaches, enabling them to better resonate and adapt with the diverse attitudes and preferences of Gen Z individuals, fostering a more effective engagement and connection within this demographic.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the respondents?
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Location
 - 1.3 Gender
2. To what extent do the three variables affect the tattoo intention?
 - 2.1 Does attitude affect the tattoo intention?
 - 2.2 Does subjective norms affect the tattoo intention?
 - 2.3 Does perceived behavioral control affect the tattoo intention?
3. What is the level of tattoo intention of Gen Z?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was strategically conducted in Valenzuela City, known for its abundant academic resources and diverse demographic which perfectly mirrored the Gen Z population. The study focused on Gen Z, individuals who represented both consumers and professionals. By exploring their engagement with tattoo culture and behaviours related to obtaining tattoos, the research aimed to reveal unique insights into how Gen Z individuals perceived body art. This location was chosen purposefully. Gen Z embodied a generation deeply connected with modern consumer trends, technology, and marketing strategies. Their distinct perspectives on tattoos and body art were crucial to this research. The study aspired to shed light on the attitudes and behaviours of these Gen Z concerning tattoos, offering comprehensive insights beyond mere statistics. These insights would have significantly contributed to academic discussions and provided

valuable guidance for marketing professionals and businesses seeking to understand and cater to the preferences of this emerging consumer group in the tattoo culture realm.

Population and Sampling

In the study, judgmental sampling, also known as purposeful sampling, was employed. Using this non-probability strategy, the researchers can select participants who have certain attributes relevant to the study based on their experience. In this case, participants were chosen based on their eligibility as belonging to Generation Z, residing in Valenzuela City, and lacking tattoos. This approach allows for a more focused and detailed inquiry compared to random sampling (Nikolopoulou, 2022).

Furthermore, the researchers utilized G*Power software to determine the appropriate sample size. G*Power is a widely used tool for calculating the minimum sample size required to detect an effect with a desired level of significance. By using this software, the researchers were able to estimate the necessary sample size to achieve a predetermined level of confidence in their findings.

This resulted in a sample size of 100 participants. Questionnaires were then administered to these 100 participants, who were selected through purposive sampling. This type of sampling deliberately targets a specific group of individuals who share common characteristics, allowing for a more focused and detailed investigation, (Ravelo, 2022).

This research targets a population of 100 Generation Z individuals in Valenzuela City who meet the following criteria: (1) 18-27 years old (inclusive); (2) both male and female; (3) with no tattoos; (4) residing in Valenzuela City; and (5) willing to participate in the study. Researchers define Generation Z as individuals born between 1997 and 2006, falling within the 18-27 age range. This age group is challenging Millennials' position as the generation with the most tattoos, as tattoos hold increasing significance for Gen Z in expressing personal beliefs, mental health, and overall well-being. Studying this specific group in Valenzuela City can offer valuable insights into their experiences with tattoos.

The study sought participants who: resided in Valenzuela City, were aged 18-27, had no tattoos, and were willing to participate. Individuals who did not meet all these criteria were ineligible.

Data Collection

The data collection serves as a summary of the data retrieval procedure used by the researcher to do the statistics required to achieve the paper's objectives. The purpose of this survey was to gather data on a variety of topics related to respondents' opinions about the desire to focus on untattooed students, particularly Gen Z in Valenzuela City. The intention of each participant to get a tattoo was evaluated holistically using a questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale. The researchers then utilize the information to determine their desire.

The respondents were expected to sign the form after reading the consent statement and must answer with honesty; respondents had given their informed consent to participate in the study. There were three demographic questions on the form on purpose. The questionnaire has three parts which is the theory of planned behaviour. For the test 1 is about attitudes. Test 2 is about subjective norms. Finally, test 3 concerns perceived behavioural control. Closed statements were also included, with the choices for answer being "Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Agree, and Strongly Agree." Complete entries were needed, and there were no deadlines. Using this survey management tool the questionnaire automatically exports data to Google Sheets, where you can easily analyse it using formulas and charts, specifically Google Forms.

Data Analysis

Mean

After carefully collecting and analysing the important data from the participants, the researchers calculated the statistical results of the test based on their responses. The data findings ultimately demonstrate the average values of the Independent and Dependent variables. Attitude has a mean of 2.87, Subjective Norms has 3.30, Perceived Behavioural Control has 2.71 and the Dependent Variable received 3.07. The mean will be the useful tool to be used because of its best measure, most reliable and influenced of all the data, Mean implies average and it is the sum of a set of data divided by the number of data. Mean can prove to be an effective tool when comparing different sets of data: however this method might be disadvantaged by the impact of extreme values

Standard Deviation

Like mean, the statistic, which is computed as the square root of the variance, that assesses a dataset's dispersion in relation to its mean. The results of computing the gathered data shows the Standard Deviation of each variable. Attitude has .76, Subjective Norms has .74, Perceived Behavioural Control has .70, and the dependent variable has .73. When analysing a dataset, it's finding the centre of the dataset, and the most common way to measure the "centre" is with the mean. The standard deviation helped the researchers to tell how measurements for the groups are spread out from the average (mean), or expected value. Basically, a small standard deviation means that the values in a statistical data set are close to the mean of the data set, on average, and vice versa.

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, or SPSS for short, is a software program used by researchers across a range of disciplines for quantitative analysis of complex data. It offers data analysis for bivariate and descriptive statistics, numerical outcome predictions, and group identification predictions. The software also provides data transformation, graphing and direct marketing features.

Multiple Regression Analysis

This statistical approach enables researchers to examine the correlation between one dependent variable and multiple independent variables to inform the decision-making process of individuals considering getting a tattoo. By utilizing this method, the intensity of the connection between the variables can be evaluated.

RESULTS

The data that the researchers collected from the survey using Google Forms is included in the portion of the paper that follows. The data gathered were appropriately examined, presented, and interpreted. The studies' conclusions reveal what tattoos Valenzuela City's Generation Z residents intend to get.

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Demographic		Frequency	Percentage
Age	Location		
18-27 yrs. Old	Valenzuela City	100	100%

This study's respondents are 100 individuals from Valenzuela City. The participants are Generation Z individuals (18-27 years old) who don't have a tattoo which completed the 100% sample of this research study.

Table 2: Descriptives

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Attitudes	100	2.87	0.76	Moderate-High
Subjective Norms	100	3.30	0.74	High
Perceived Behavioral Control	100	2.71	0.70	Moderate-High
Tattoo Intention	100	3.07	0.07	Moderate-High

The presented data highlights the significant impact of Subjective Norms on Tattoo Intention, suggesting a high influence (3.30 Mean). In terms of Attitudes, the interpretation points to a Moderate-High effect (2.87 Mean), showcasing its noteworthy role. Perceived behavioral Control is also notable with a Moderate-High effect (2.71 Mean), indicating its influence on Tattoo Intention. Overall, the comprehensive analysis underscores the complex interplay between Attitudes, Subjective Norms, and Perceived Behavioral Control in shaping Tattoo Intention.

Table 3: Linear Regression

Table 3.1: Attitudes

Variable	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Unstandardized beta	Decision rule and Interpretation
Attitudes and Tattoo Intention	0.611	0.239	0.121	Accept Null Ho1: Attitude is not a significant predictor of tattoo intention

The table above shows how Attitudes affect the tattoo intention. The results show the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression obtaining a p-value of .239. The null hypothesis was accepted based on the decision rule that instructs the researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05. The p-value of .239 which is greater than 0.05 resulted in the null hypothesis being accepted. As a result, attitude is not a significant predictor of tattoo intention. As a result, Attitude is not a significant predictor of tattoo intention. There is also a high correlation (.611) between the two variables, and each unit of Attitude has a .121 increase in tattoo intention.

Table 3.2: Subjective Norms

Variable	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Unstandardized beta	Decision rule and Interpretation
Subjective Norms and Tattoo Intention	0.714	0.001	0.486	Reject Ho1: Subjective Norms is not a significant predictor of tattoo intention

The table above shows how Subjective norms affect the tattoo intention. The results show the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression obtaining a p-value of 0.001. The null hypothesis was rejected based on the decision rule that instructs the researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05. Because the p-value was less than 0.05 (0.001), the null hypothesis was rejected. As a result, Subjective Norm is a significant predictor of tattoo intention. There is also a high correlation (.714) between the two variables, and each unit of Attitude has a .486 increase in tattoo intention.

Table 3.3: Perceived Behavioral Control

Variable	Pearson Correlation	P-Value	Unstandardized beta	Decision rule and Interpretation
Perceived Behavioral Control and Tattoo Intention	0.692	0.003	0.338	Reject Ho1: Perceived Behavioral Control is not a significant predictor of tattoo intention

The table above shows how Perceived Behavioral Control affects tattoo intention. The results show the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression obtaining a p-value of 0.009. The null hypothesis was rejected based on the decision rule that instructs the researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis was rejected due to the p-value of 0.001, which is less than

0.05. As a result, Perceived Behavioral Control is a significant predictor of tattoo intention. There is also a high correlation (.692) between the two variables, and each unit of Attitude has a .338 increase in tattoo intention.

DISCUSSION

In this study, the researchers focused on understanding the tattoo intention of Generation Z individuals in Valenzuela City. The data collection process involved administering a survey through Google Forms, and the gathered data was meticulously presented, analyzed, and interpreted. Important insights can be gained from the study participants' demographic profile, which is displayed in Table 1. The 100 responders, comprising 100% of the sample, range in age from 12 to 27. Furthermore, all participants are residents of Valenzuela City and share the common characteristic of not having a tattoo.

The demographic data highlights the specificity of the study's target group Generation Z individuals residing in Valenzuela City who have not yet engaged in tattooing. This careful selection of participants ensures a focused investigation into the factors influencing tattoo intention within this particular demographic. The emphasis on age, location, and the absence of tattoos among the respondents sets a clear foundation for the subsequent analysis, allowing for a targeted exploration of the psychological factors influencing tattoo intentions among this specific group of individuals.

In Table 2, the study presents descriptive statistics for key variables, shedding light on the attitudes and intentions of the Generation Z individuals in Valenzuela City regarding tattoos. Upon examining the variable "Attitudes," it is evident that the mean score is 2.87 and the standard deviation is 0.76. This indicates a noteworthy level of attitudes towards tattoos among the respondents, falling on the higher end of the spectrum. This implies a diverse range of opinions within the surveyed population.

Subjective Norms shows that society norms had a considerable influence on individuals' intentions to have tattoos, with a mean of 3.30 and a standard deviation of 0.74. The findings imply that cultural beliefs and outside influences have a big influence on how Valenzuela City's Generation Z residents feel about having tattoos.

With a mean of 2.71 and a standard deviation of 0.70, perceived behavioral control points to a moderate to high degree of perceived control over the choice to get inked. This implies that respondents feel they have a considerable degree of agency in determining whether to engage in tattooing, aligning with the theory of planned behavior.

The "Tattoo Intention" variable shows a moderate to high level of intention among the respondents to acquire a tattoo, with a mean of 3.07 and a standard deviation of 0.73. According to this research, Valenzuela City's Generation Z population exhibits a

significant propensity to have tattoos on average. This tendency may be influenced by the people's attitudes, subjective norms, and sense of behavioral control.

Overall, these descriptive results provide a comprehensive overview of the psychological factors influencing tattoo intention within the studied demographic, offering valuable insights into the prevailing attitudes and perceptions shaping their decision-making processes.

In the study that is being presented, the effects of three major variables—Attitudes, Subjective Norms, and Perceived Behavioral Control—on tattoo intention are examined using linear regression. First, attitudes have a strong positive link with tattoo intention, as seen by the obtained Pearson link of .611. Nonetheless, the non-significant p-value of .239 indicates that attitude is not a significant predictor of tattoo intention, supporting the null hypothesis. The absence of statistical significance indicates that, despite the substantial correlation, care should be taken when establishing a direct causal relationship.

The P-value is the likelihood that the current finding would have been discovered if the correlation coefficient (or null hypothesis) had actually been zero. Statistical significance is achieved when the correlation coefficient is less than the traditional threshold of 5% ($P < 0.05$).

Subjective Norms follow, where a significant positive link with tattoo intention is indicated by a Pearson link of .714. Due to the low p-value of .001, which indicates that Subjective Norms is a significant predictor of tattoo intention, the null hypothesis is rejected. Its predictive power in this context is further supported by the unstandardized beta of .486 which shows that every unit rise in Subjective Norms is related with a significant increase in tattoo intention.

Lastly, Perceived Behavioral Control exhibits a Pearson Correlation of .692 and a significant p-value of .009, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that Perceived Behavioral Control is a significant predictor of tattoo intention. The unstandardized beta of .338 suggests a moderate increase in tattoo intention for each unit increase in Perceived Behavioral Control.

Conclusions

This study assessed the amount of Gen Z people in Valenzuela City who do not currently have tattoos as well as whether or not attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control had an impact on these people's intentions. In conclusion, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control will be the primary determinants. These two indicators demonstrate how people are more inclined to think about getting a tattoo if people in their social networks think it looks good. And when members of Generation Z feel confident that they can get a tattoo without suffering consequences. Although attitudes are a non-significant predictor, this indicates that Gen Z may make decisions

based more on perceived control and social pressure than on their internal thoughts about the future.

This thesis's use of the survey method to examine Gen Z's tattoo effect has been crucial in obtaining a wide range of viewpoints and views. Through the application of this methodology, a thorough comprehension of the reasons behind, attitudes toward, and social ramifications related to tattoo intentions in this population has been attained. The methodical data gathering made possible by the survey's structured methodology allowed for a detailed examination of the various aspects affecting Gen Z's tattoo decision-making process.

It's crucial to recognize any potential survey methodology drawbacks, such as self-reporting biases or the incapacity to fully capture the breadth of individual experiences. Subsequent investigations may examine augmenting quantitative techniques with qualitative approaches to further explore the individual stories and affective components behind tattoo aspirations.

Recommendations

Recommendation Based on the Findings

The researchers made this study to assess the tattoo intention of Generation Z with the use of three variables. The findings showed that the tattoo is accepted by generation Z and seen as an art and expression. Therefore, the researchers suggest to the marketers and business owners that the tattoo is a good business because it is now more accepted by today's generation because according to Statista Research Department (2021), " 23% of Gen Z have at least one tattoo compared to other generations. " so it will be booming in the future since the new generation is more accepting of it. The study also discovered that among the three variables used in Tattoo Intentions, attitude was the closest to the significance level of not being a significant predictor of Tattoo Intention, leading the researchers to recommend to business owners and marketers to create a strategy that can educate people that Tattoo is not Bad. In terms of the variable that has the highest unstandardized data, Subjective Norm was recognized to have the highest number and considered to be the most significant predictor of Tattoo Intentions. Leading the researchers to target social norms, trends, create a tattoo community, and create inspiring stories for advertisements and acquiring well known celebrities when offering tattoos, always focus on the trend and be artistic with it, to get the attention of Generation Z and which will make the chances for them to generate profit.

Based on the results of the analyzed data, Subjective Norms is the variable that is highly correlated between the two variables, which means that Subjective Norms highly affects the level of tattoo intention. Considering the positive perception of tattoos among Generation Z, businesses in the tattoo industry should focus on educational campaigns to dispel any negative stereotypes. Additionally, leveraging social norms, trends, and

celebrity endorsements can enhance marketing strategies, creating a vibrant and artistic image to attract Generation Z and maximize profit potential.

Recommendation for Future Research

In order to deeply explore attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioral perception, it is crucial for researchers to utilize a mixed-methods approach that combines qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques. By integrating these methods, crucial insights can be gained, providing a comprehensive understanding of both personal experiences and statistical patterns.

Moreover, employing experimental designs that manipulate variables of interest can help establish causal relationships, offering insights into the direct impact of attitude and subjective norms on behavioral perception. The study's findings' validity and robustness may be enhanced by this experimental rigor.

In terms of refining the Subjective Norm variable, researchers should conduct in-depth interviews or focus groups to explore the underlying beliefs and social influences shaping participants' perceptions. This qualitative exploration can unveil nuances that may not be captured by quantitative measures alone.

Lastly, to address potential biases, researchers should implement strategies for participant validation, ensuring that responses align with genuine attitudes and behavioral intentions. Utilizing triangulation methods, such as comparing self-reported data with observed behaviors, can enhance the credibility of the findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher and their team are committed to ensuring that reviewers, members of the ethics board, and participants are all equipped with comprehensive information in order to fully understand the scope of any study being conducted under their supervision. This includes providing participants with detailed information on the study's objectives and design. There would also be extremely particular procedures for collecting and handling the data. The primary investigator of the project would provide all informants with contact details in case any ethical concerns or complaints emerged throughout the research period; these would be addressed by the local ethics commission.

Safeguarding the welfare of study participants is a need for the researcher and/or research team. This includes protecting information gleaned from document reviews that can be deemed sensitive due to factors such as race, ethnicity, religion, politics, health, or sexual orientation. According to research ethics, the researcher is obligated to uphold several principles, chief among them being secrecy. As researchers, it is our responsibility

to ensure that all data gathered from or shared by human subjects upholds their autonomy and dignity, while also respecting the rights of individuals and groups.

Every participant in the research would always provide their informed consent before beginning any study project, according to the researcher and/or research team. This would require full disclosure of all possible hazards to the participants, together with information about the methodology, data processing, and whether or not respondents would receive compensation.

REFERENCES

- Abellán, G. B., López, J. D. S., De La Rosa, M. M., González, Á. L., Rabanales-Sotos, J., & Hidalgo, J. L. (2022). *Attitudes towards Tattoos among Spanish Health Science Students*. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 12(12), 1719–1728. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ejihpe12120121>
- Baumann, C., Timming, A. R., & Gollan, P. J. (2016). *Taboo tattoos? A study of the gendered effects of body art on consumers' attitudes toward visibly tattooed front line staff*. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 29, 31–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2015.11.005>
- Colonno, I. (2023, September 19). *Newer generations, more tattoos, less taboos*. *Daily Forty-Niner*. <https://daily49er.com/artslife/2023/09/18/newer-generations-more-tattoos-less-taboos/>
- Forbes, G. B. (2001). *College Students with Tattoos and Piercings: Motives, Family Experiences, Personality Factors, and Perception by Others*. *Psychological Reports*, 89(3), 774–786. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pr0.2001.89.3.774>
- Ravelo, C. (2022, November 29). *How to determine sample size from G*Power*. *Statistics Solutions*. <https://www.statisticssolutions.com/how-to-determine-sample-size-from-gpower/>
- Roeloffs, M. W. (2023, August 15). *Tattoo USA: One-Third of Americans have ink as industry projected to hit \$4 billion*. *Forbes*. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/maryroeloffs/2023/08/15/tattoo-usa-one-third-of-americans-have-ink-as-industry-projected-to-hit-4-billion/?sh=5769b30621e0>
- Drews, D. R., Allison, C. K., & Probst, J. R. (2000). *Behavioral and Self-Concept differences in tattooed and non tattooed college students*. *Psychological Reports*, 86(2), 475–481. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pr0.2000.86.2.475>
- King, K. A., & Vidourek, R. A. (2013). *Getting inked: Tattoo and risky behavioral involvement among university students*. *Social Science Journal*, 50(4), 540–546. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soscij.2013.09.009>
- Brookes, E. (2023, October 11). *The Theory of planned Behavior: Behavioral intention*. *SimplyPsychology*. https://www.simplypsychology.org/theory-of-planned-behavior.html?fbclid=IwAR0Zbl6o6f4RyZQg2xgfuPxQv_2SkjUbrpC8V_e_JFRW3VgNdkxAVXtJ0Uw
- Nikolopoulou K. (2022). *What Is Purposive Sampling? Definition & Examples*. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/purposive-sampling/>

APPENDIX

Research Instrument and Likert Four-point Scale Range Interpretation

POINT	SCALE RANGE	EXPLANATION
4	4.00 - 3.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.99 – 2.00	Agree
2	1.99 – 1.00	Disagree
1	1.00 – 0.99	Strongly Disagree

<u>Mean Range</u>	<u>Interpretation</u>
1.00 – 1.74	Low
1.75 – 2.49	Moderate Low
2.50 – 3.24	Moderate-High
3.25 – 4.00	High

Questions	4	3	2	1
1. I believe that tattoos are a form of self-expression				
2. I consider tattoo as an artwork				
3. I would feel more confident with a tattoo				
4. I believe that tattoos are meaningful.				
5. Having a tattoo is part of my culture				
6. The people that surround me would be supportive of me getting a tattoo.				

7. I believe that tattoo have a significant value in the society				
8. I would feel more accepted by the community if I had a tattoo				
9. I am confident that I can get a tattoo if I want to.				
10. I believe that I have the skills and resources necessary to get a tattoo.				
11. I feel like I have control over whether or not I get a tattoo.				
12. I am not afraid of the pain or discomfort associated with getting a tattoo.				
13. I am very likely to get a tattoo in the future.				
14. I have already started planning a tattoo design.				
15. I have researched tattoo artists in my area.				
16. I have discussed getting a tattoo with my friends and family.				

Scoring:

The **Attitude** subscale items are **Q1, Q2, Q3, and Q4**. The **Subjective Norm** subscale items are **Q5, Q6, Q7, and Q8**. The **Perceived Behavioral Control** subscale items are **Q9, Q10, Q11, and Q12**. The **Tattoo Intention** subscale items are **Q13, Q14, Q15, and Q16**.